

Initial Design of a Communicative Regional Organizational Structure

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ABSTRACT: After the enactment of UU Nomor 22 Tahun 1999 concerning Regional Government, the era of regional autonomy also applies throughout Indonesia. The impact is that there is a "division" and "transfer" of power from the central government to the regions. The implication is that organizational design must be discussed based on contemporary Job Design thinking. The goal is that we can produce a more communicative organizational structure in the realm of regional autonomy in two types or forms of organization. *First*, mechanistic organizational design - which is characterized by, among others, very high horizontal differentiation, cold and rigid hierarchical relationships, the obligation to carry out fixed tasks, high formalization accompanied by the use of very formal communication channels, and centralized decision-making authority. *Second*, the characteristics of an organic organization, namely an organization that has very low horizontal differentiation (read: for example, the difference in job content between several work units is very small). If this happens, then theoretically we can reduce the number of bureaus or sections, the method is by collaborating, namely vertical and horizontal mergers'

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1. INTRODUCTION

After the enactment UU Nomor 22 Tahun 1999 concerning Regional Government, then it also applies the era of regional autonomy also came into effect throughout Indonesia. Since then, all district and city governments, as well as provinces, have submitted Draft Regional Regulations on Organizational Structure to adjust to the Law. (*Note*, UU Nomor 22/1999 is no longer valid, replaced by UU Nomor 23 Tahun 2014) concerning Regional Government; however, efforts to reconstruct the organizational structure are still being carried out by the Central Government and Regional Governments) (Brendanm 1997).

In its journey after the Regional Regulation on Organizational Structure (Regional Secretariat, Service, Agency, Office, Institution, etc.) was formed and implemented, many problems arose. One of the problems that always arises is the occurrence of "overlapping" of duties and functions between one service and another, between one sub-service and another sub-service within one service. This situation will affect formal communication in these organizations. In connection with this problem, I will provide a brief description of how to design an organizational structure in such a way that the structure is communicative. Why is that? I am of the opinion that no matter how sophisticated the organizational structure is, all organizational structures are certainly formed for one main purpose, to facilitate communication between humans, communication between individuals and groups within the organization.

2. REORGANIZATION THAT LOSES MEANING

Thomas Bridges (1997) in his book *The Culture of Citizenship: Inventing Post-modern Civic Culture* states that: in the state environment there needs to be an increase in the intellectual abilities of politicians, there needs to be a change in the political morals of politicians, there needs to be an improvement in the political environment as a whole. Only in this way can a Reinventing Government occur. It turns out that in many ways reinventing government is very dependent on the extent to which the inventing of the culture of citizenship occurs (Baubock, 1994), meaning that the "rediscovery" of the characteristics of government is also determined by one variable, namely the renewal of the culture of society, including the renewal of the culture of government apparatus, whether executive, legislative or judiciary. If no renewal at the community level is carried out, then reinventing government is in vain.

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The regional government (province, district and city) is very aware of this so that immediately after UU Nomor 22 Tahun 1999 was effectively implemented in 2001, the executive and legislative initiatives submitted a Draft Regional Regulation on the organizational structure of government in accordance with the demands of reform (Brettell, 2011).

I would like to quote again the opinion of Toonen and Raadschelders (see: Theo A. J. Toonen Public Sector Reform in Western Europa in the background paper for the presentation on public sector reform in Western Europa, 5-8 April 1997) which reminds us of the "lust for reform". He said, now, after the reform, we seem to be possessed by lust, the lust to reform anything, as a result the reform produced in 1998 began to lose direction as was once expressed in many mass media as "excessive reform". In order to channel the "desire for reform" in an orderly manner, the regional government, whether it is a province or district/city, needs to determine: (1) the subject of reform, so what scope will be reformed; and (2) the degree of "feeling" of the change process.

First, with the subject of reform, it is hoped that the sectors to be reformed will be determined or selected. These subjects can be determined by considering; (1) the purpose of reform, so what do we need to reform first, whether to reform values, norms or principles (Freixas, 2003); (2) means of reformation, which relates to the steps or ways of reform, whether natural resources, human resources, cultural resources to technological resources (Hoffmann, 2005); (3) whether we only carry out reform on taxes, regional income related to human resources and natural resources (Straffin, 1983); (4) institutional reform, so only certain aspects are reformed, for example regulations in the legal field, regulations and legislation, the relationship between subsystems of the reformed sectors (interfaces) (Darwall, 1995); and (5) do we reform privatization, decentralization and good and honest government management programs as political policy managers? (Driver, 2004).

Second, the degree of "feeling" for change. For example, can we carry out a transformation including the transformation of the organizational structure and work procedures of all organizations in the regions on a large scale (this concept is called rationalization) (Aswathappa, 2008). If this happens, the government will face an extraordinary challenge because when rationalization occurs, problems arise for the bureaucracy (especially if the "new bureaucracy" carries out a cleansing of an "old bureaucracy" regime); for example: there are thousands of people who are forced to retire early, there are thousands of officials who lose their positions, and the accumulation of other problems that will disrupt the social and economic scale in a broad sense, or in other words, bureaucratic rationalization will leave behind new shocks on a large scale. Therefore, theoretically it should be remembered that the practice of changing the structure of government organizations must be placed in the "dimension of change" which conceptually exists in the corridor; reform, transition, changes, adaptation, modernization, innovation, reinvention, reorganization, rediscovering or improving influence (reshaping) (Robbins, 2009).

3. THE PROCESS OF CHANGING THE VALUE STRUCTURE

I suspect that all RANPERDA and PERDA on the organizational structure and work procedures of regional government organizations revolve around two things: (1) laying the foundations for organizing the organization (foundation of organizing) of provincial/district governments (Bovaird, 2003) and (2) we choose (from many) problems and then determine the organizational design (organization and job design) (Azfar etc, 1999). These two aspects can be seen in table 1.

If we pay attention to the two main questions above, then the discussion of the organizational structure, both those that are already running and those that will continue to be discussed, should not just be changing the structure of an organization to organize work procedures but rather changing a structure of values and norms, the mental structure of government officials to be in accordance with the spirit of reform for improving services to the community (Bovaird, 2003). In addition UU Nomor Tahun 1999, implicitly requires changes to the "government service structure" directly to districts and cities as a form of responsible regional autonomy.

The implication of UU Nomor 22 Tahun 1999 is that the improvement of the organizational structure should be directed more towards districts/cities to bring services closer to the community and not primarily at the provincial level, therefore the provincial level should have a much simpler structure. Based on this level of thinking, now is the time to change the vision and mission of the concept of "organizing" so that we are not trapped in the realm of thinking of classical organizational studies as seen in the table (I-A - 1 to 5) (Johnson, 2001). This trap still shrouds the knowledge of government officials (executives, especially organizational designers) and is responded to more or less the same by the legislature in general.

We can take an example from the news of the mass media in the country about changes in the organizational structure of the work system of regional government organizations, where we are presented with a series of shallow debates about departmentalization (I-A - B) (Prasojo, 2006). In this case, with the globalization that is sweeping the world today and the reforms that are taking place in Indonesia, the concept of designing organizational structures should be more contemporary because organizational structures are greatly influenced by changes in the social, political, economic and technological environments, and therefore we need a new government strategy towards a new Indonesia with a new, more appropriate organizational size (see Figure 2).

Therefore, in my opinion, our mindset should start to move from the state (I- A - 1 to 5) to (I – B – 1 to 5) (Thoha, 2004). This means that the mindset about the concept of division of labor, unity of command, authority and responsibility, span of control and departmentalization must be immediately moved to contemporary thinking. In contemporary thinking, the concept of: (1) unity of command is only recognized as useful in certain situations that are coercive; (2) authority and responsibility must shift from the classical view that focuses authority on the line (work units that carry out the main tasks of the organization, for example regional services, as well as the practice of chain command from the top echelon officials to the lower echelon officials, and the authority of staff (elements that assist the leadership) also changes towards the formation of power, namely the capacity to influence a decision that involves all levels of the organization (read: echelons).

Based on this idea, all levels of office or echelons that were once regulated by (Peraturan Pemerintah Nomor 84 Tahun 2000 are still theoretically recognized in organizational communication science as having a form of power to force (coercive power), namely the power of a leader over subordinates as part of the duties and functions that are his responsibility. Echelon officials also have the power to give rewards (reward power), namely the power of an official based on his capacity. In addition, these officials also have legitimate power, namely to validate what should be done by their subordinates. The final power is power due to "expert power" which allows an official (because he is considered to know his duties and functions precisely) to be trusted to say and work correctly so that what he does and says is used as a reference (refent power) by his subordinates.

4. ORGANIZATIONAL DESIGN

With the various variations of power, the organizational design in the future must be discussed based on contemporary Job Design thinking as seen in the table (II – C - 1 and 2 and II D 1 to 4) whose output is (III E 1 to 6). Finally, we can produce a more communicative organizational structure in the realm of regional autonomy in two types or forms of organization.

First, a mechanistic organizational design. A mechanistic organization is characterized by, among others, very high horizontal differentiation, cold and rigid hierarchical relations, the obligation to carry out fixed tasks, high formalization accompanied by the use of very formal communication channels, and centralized decision-making authority (Rondinelli, 1983). This structure is actually the same as the classical approach (I – A- 1 to 5) and at the same time describes the state of the existing.

There are two reasons for the formation of this mechanistic structure; namely: (1) functional organizational structure (Begg, 1995) - What is meant by a functional organizational structure is a structure formed by several groups or work units that are the same (or whose work content is almost the same) in tasks and functions or specializations, or there is close cooperation between these units; and to (2) a divisional organizational structure, namely an organizational structure formed by highly autonomous work units and by which the work units can work very independently (Stigles, 1975).

With this basis of thinking, to prevent the presence of an unclear number of work units (whether services, agencies, offices, institutions, etc.) from government organizations (because they are weak in terms of "functional structure", then through the "mechanistic organizational design" (Bennet, 1990) approach we need to change it into a divisional structure so that it will be easier to become a more dynamic organization (no longer organic).

Second, the characteristics of an organic organization are organizations that have very low horizontal differentiation (read: for example, the difference in work content/job content between several work units is very small) (Kellermann, 1997). If this happens, then theoretically we can reduce the number of bureaus or sections, the method is to collaborate, namely vertical and horizontal mergers as shown in Figure 3.

An example of a vertical merger is done by uniting or merging the Biro PEMDES at the Provincial Secretariat into the Village Community Empowerment Agency, or the Program Preparation Bureau into the Provincial BAPPEDA, etc. While a horizontal merger can be done by uniting the PEMDES Bureau with the Biro TATA ORGANISASI, or the Biro Umum with the Biro HUMAS, the Legal Bureau with the Biro TATA ORGANISASI, the Biro Ekonomi with the Biro Penyusunan Program dll, etc. (see explanation of job enlargement and job enrichment). As a result, new work units that will be formed when starting a new task can easily adapt to each other.

Referring UU Nomor 22 tahun 1999 (it would be better if this discussion was expanded and deepened with a legal and governmental approach, and I am not authorized to explain this approach), the effectiveness of ideal organizational communication is to display a simple organizational structure from the choice of organizational design - organic design (II D - 1) namely a simple organizational structure. Simplicity is largely determined by the decreasing number of organizational structures or layers (read: the number of echelons is decreasing), increasing functional roles so that organizational communication is more flexible. To fulfill the above requirements, when the executive prepares a draft of the organizational structure of a new service, agency or institution in the context

of regional autonomy, the legislative, provincial and district/city DPRD should not be hasty, because both the executive and the legislative still need to get an explanation of the theoretical approach in order to change the design of the organizational structure.

However, theoretically, the choice of a new organizational structure needs to be supported by a job design option analysis as shown in table (III - E). What is meant by job design is the way or steps in which the tasks of an organization are combined into a more complete form of tasks. Which are the ways or steps? Here, a shared understanding is needed about the supporting factors of job design, namely job specialization, job rotation, job enlargement, and job enrichment, to form a work team and in accordance with the job characteristic model.

This also means that a job specification-specialization analysis is needed, namely determining the formation of a unit based on the specificity of the unit's tasks, especially if supported by specialist personnel. If we move from the existing organizational sources, then from the specialization analysis we can determine job enlargement and job enrichment.

What is meant by job enlargement is the expansion of the tasks of an organizational unit horizontally in order to increase the scope of tasks (job scope). While job enrichment is the expansion of the tasks of an organizational unit vertically by adding tasks so that the responsibility in the planning and responsibility functions is greater (note: this article will not discuss Marxist organizational structures, work networks and splinter structures in the form of task forces and committee organizations). And all of this is very much determined by factors, both individual and group, which have variations in skills, clarity of task identity, significance of tasks and autonomy, etc.

For me, the most important thing is that the work to discuss the structure related to the formation of new organizational structures in the regions must be able to pay attention to various theoretical approaches so that a practice can be found that can be run optimally. In that way, at least we have met two demands and challenges of the regional government (Magen, 2008). *First*, how the spirit and implementation of regional autonomy are able to resolve various regional demands and our internal problems as a nation, such as the threat of disintegration, socio-economic disparities between regions, efforts to suppress justice in the social, economic, legal fields, etc (Borsel, 2009). *Second*, how the spirit and implementation of regional autonomy are able to respond to various demands of rapidly changing global dynamics with competency requirements.

Both demands should encourage all parties to seek win-win solutions and synergies, so that the implementation of regional autonomy can run well. At least regional autonomy does not lead to the deconstruction of the spirit of national and state life into a regional or tribal spirit that gives rise to various conflicts and tensions. If in the past unity was upheld on the pillars of diversity, now unity should be built on uniqueness and differences in accordance with Bhineka Tunggal Ika.

I. The Basics of Organizing		II. Choice of Organizational Form and Job Design	
A. Basic concepts of organizational design *)	B. Contemporary Organizational Design Concepts	C. Mechanical design options	D. Organic design options
1. Division of labor	1. Organizations that are mechanistic and organic	1. Functional structure	1. Simple structure
2. Unity of command	2. Structural changes according to strategy	2. Divisional structure	2. Matrix structure
3. Authority and responsibility	3. Authority and responsibility		1. Network structure
4. Span of control	4. Structure and technology		2. Additional structure
5. Departmentalization	5. Structure and environment	III. E - Job design option	
*) Note - both A 1 to 5 have classical and contemporary discussions.		1. Specialization 2. Rotation 3. Job enlargement 4. Job enrichment 5. Work teams (team integration and team autonomy) 6. Task characteristic model	

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LEGEND

- Badan Pemberdayaan Masyarakat Desa (Village Community Empowerment Agency)
- Badan Perencanaan dan Penelitian Daerah (BAPPEDA) (Regional Planning and Research Agency)
- Bhineka Tunggal Ika (a concept that explains different but still one, this writing is under the feet of the Garuda bird, the symbol of the Republic of Indonesia).
- Biro Ekonomi (Economic Bureau)
- Biro Hubungan Masyarakat (HUMAS) (Public Relations Bureau)

- Biro Hukum (Legal Bureau)
- Biro Pemerintahan Desa (PEMDES) (Village Government Bureau)
- Biro Penyusunan Program (Program Preparation Bureau)
- Biro Tata Organisasi (Organizational Administration Bureau)
- Biro Tata Pemerintahan (TATAPEM) (Governance Administration Bureau)
- Biro Umum (General Bureau)
- Peraturan Daerah (PERDA) (Regional Regulation)
- Peraturan Pemerintah (Government Regulation)
- Rancangan Peraturan Daerah (RANPERDA) (Draft Regional Regulation)
- UU Nomor 22 Tahun 1999 tentang Pemerintahan Daerah (Law Number 22 of 1999 Concerning Regional Government)